

**A RANDOMIZED OPEN LABELLED COMPARATIVE CLINICAL STUDY TO
EVALUATE THE EFFICACY OF PRACHHANNA FOLLOWED BY GUNJA LEPA AND
PRP THERAPY FOLLOWED BY APPLICATION OF MINOXIDIL SOLUTION IN THE
MANAGEMENT OF INDRALUPTA W.S.R TO ALOPECIA AREATA- A COMPARITIVE
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ABSTRACT

Alopecia areata is defined as a common, non-scarring, autoimmune condition characterized by patchy hair loss, typically affecting the scalp but potentially involving any hair-bearing area of the body. The global incidence of Alopecia Areata is approximately 0.2% annually, affecting around 2% of the population at some point in their lifetime. Indralupta, described in Ayurvedic texts as one of the Shirokapalagata roga in which Vata and Pitta dosha primarily destroys the hair follicle later Kapha and Rakta causes Srotas avarodha further leading to stoppage of regrowth. It aligns closely with Alopecia areata, an autoimmune condition in modern dermatology. This clinical study evaluates the comparative efficacy of *Prachhanna karma* followed by *Guñjā lepa* (Group A) versus Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) therapy with topical Minoxidil 5% (Group B) in 40 patients diagnosed with Indralupta. Each group comprised 20 patients treated over 45 days. Group A showed superior results in hair regrowth and symptomatic relief. Hair loss reduction reached 36.0% by Day 15, 76.0% by Day 30, and 88.0% by Day 45. Itching reduced by 40.0%, 77.1%, and 94.3% across the same intervals. Group B showed hair loss reduction of 16.0%, 52.0%, and 68.0%, and itching relief of 22.2%, 55.6%, and 81.5%, respectively. Overall improvement was 91.14% in Group A and 74.74% in Group B. The study concludes that *Prachhanna* followed by *Guñjā lepa* offers a more holistic and effective approach for Indralupta, addressing both Dosha imbalance and follicular regeneration.

KEYWORDS: Indralupta, Alopecia areata, *Prachhanna karma*, *Guñjā lepa*, PRP therapy, Minoxidil, Ayurveda.**INTRODUCTION**

Human hair naturally grows and falls as part of a normal cycle. However, in some individuals, the rate of hair fall exceeds the rate of hair growth. When hair falls from the follicles (i.e., the hair roots), the chances of regrowth from that point are almost negligible. The result is baldness; in medical terms, this condition is called **alopecia**.^[1]

Ayurveda has described hair problems under *Kśudra Roga*^[2] and *Śiroroga*^[3], such as **Khālitya**^[4], **Pālitya**^[5],

Indralupta^[6], etc. *Indralupta* is a specific condition characterized by hair loss in patches in certain areas of the scalp due to the vitiation of **Tridosha** and **Rakta Dhātu**. Pitta, associated with Vāta, lodges in the **Romakūpa** causing hair fall. Later, Kapha associated with Rakta obstructs the hair roots and restricts regrowth. *Indralupta* is categorized among **Kapālagata Roga**^[7] and *Kśudraroga* by Vagbhata and is characterized by loss of hair.

There are several types of alopecia depending on the pattern of hair loss. **Alopecia areata** is a disorder in which hair loss occurs in patches, causing baldness without scarring of the affected area.^[8] It can affect the entire scalp. Modern lifestyle factors, avoidance of regular head baths, the use of harmful shampoos, and allergic manifestations, reduced body resistance, hormonal imbalance, and malnutrition leads to poor hygiene of scalp. Currently, management for Alopecia areata include Topical corticosteroids eg Flucinolone acetonide cream, Intralesional corticosteroids e.g. Hydrocortisone acetate, Topical immunotherapy e.g. DNCB (Dinitrochlorobenzene). Most of them have adverse affects such as Skin rash, Atrophy^[9] etc. Platelet rich plasma Therapy is considered as effective Ayurveda suggests surgical procedures like Siravyadha, Pracchanna, Lekhana and para surgical procedure like Jalookavacharana in Indralupta. Large numbers of drugs for external application in the form of herbal, mineral and single drugs are also described. Many curative and preventive measures like nasya, Rasayana, moordha taila^[10] (Abhyanga, Pichu, Shirodhara, Shirobasti), pathya sevana, apathya nisheda are also mentioned.

Modern science identifies *Alopecia areata* as an autoimmune disorder mediated by T-lymphocytes targeting anagen hair follicles. Genetic predisposition, environmental triggers, and immune dysregulation contribute to its onset and progression. Despite the availability of treatments such as corticosteroids, immunotherapy, topical vasodilators (e.g., Minoxidil), and Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) therapy, the unpredictable course and variable response rates necessitate exploration of alternative modalities.^[11] PRP therapy, in particular, has gained attention for its regenerative potential via growth factor enrichment and follicular stimulation.

The present study is designed to evaluate and compare the efficacy of two distinct therapeutic approaches.

- **Group A:** *Prachhanna Karma* followed by *Guñjā Lepa*.
- **Group B:** *PRP therapy* followed by topical *Minoxidil 5%* application.

This comparative clinical trial was conducted on 40 patients diagnosed with Alopecia areata, equated to *Indralupta* based on classical Ayurvedic descriptions. The study aims to assess therapeutic outcomes in terms of hair regrowth, reduction in itching, and overall improvement in scalp condition, while also documenting adverse reactions and patient-reported experiences.

The rationale for this investigation stems from the need to bridge traditional Ayurvedic wisdom with contemporary biomedical insights. By analyzing the mechanisms of action, doshic involvement, and clinical efficacy of both treatment protocols, the study seeks to contribute to evidence-based integrative dermatology. Furthermore, it emphasizes the importance of localized

detoxification (*Raktamokshana*), follicular stimulation, and immune modulation in managing chronic scalp disorders.

This thesis endeavors to present a comprehensive understanding of *Indralupta/Alopecia areata*, its dual pathology, and the therapeutic potential of combining ancient surgical techniques with herbal pharmacology, juxtaposed against modern regenerative interventions. The findings are expected to inform clinical practice, enhance therapeutic outcomes, and pave the way for future interdisciplinary research in trichology and Ayurvedic dermatology.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- To evaluate the efficacy of Prachhanna followed by Gunja lepa in the management of Indralupta w.s.r to Alopecia areata.
- To evaluate the efficacy of PRP Therapy followed by application of Minoxidil solution in the management of Indralupta w.s.r Alopecia areata.
- To compare the efficacy of Prachanna followed by gunja lepa and PRP Therapy followed by application of Minoxidil solution in the management of Indralupta w.s.r to Alopecia areata.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study design

A comparative clinical study containing 40 patients diagnosed as Indralupta w.s.r to Alopecia areata, were included for the study and was randomly allotted into 2 groups namely Group-A (Prachhanna followed by Gunja lepa) and Group-B (PRP Therapy followed by application of minoxidil solution) with 20 patients each.

B. Source of patients

A total number of 40 patients diagnosed as Indralupta of either sex was selected from OPD and IPD of Taranath Government. Ayurvedic medical college and hospital, Ballari.

DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients will be selected between 16--60 years of age, irrespective of sex, religion, occupation.
2. Specific signs and symptoms of Indralupta (Sudden patchy hairloss, Itching).
3. No active infection at the site of Alopecia areata.
4. Diabetes mellitus (under control).
5. Hypertension (under control).

Exclusion criteria

1. If Hb% less than 10gm%
2. History of Malignancy.
3. Bleeding disorders.
4. Alopecia associated with systemic diseases
5. Positive cases of HIV and HBsAg.

INVESTIGATIONS

- CBC, ESR, RBS, CT, BT, HBs Ag, HIV 1&2

MATERIALS REQUIRED FOR STUDY**For Prachhanna followed by Gunja lepa**

- Sterile gloves
- Sterile gauze and pads
- Local antiseptic drug
- Surgical blade
- Gunja lepa

For PRP Therapy followed by minoxidil solution

- Sterile gloves
- Sterile gauze and pads
- Insulin syringe
- Fresh centrifuged plasma
- Sterile disposable syringe
- 5% Minoxidil solution

PROCEDURE**Group A: Prachhanna Followed by Gunja lepa**

Poorva Karma.

Cleanse the alopecia areata with antiseptic solution.

Pradhana Karma

The Surgical blade no.11 is taken and given the Uniform incisions that are straight, not too superficial and not too deep, neither Too close nor too distant

Incisions should be made upto Occurrence of pin point bleeding(approx. 1-2mm depth)

Incisions should be 0.5 to 1 cm apart from each other.

Wait until the shuddha rakta (Brick red) arrives after removal of Dushta rakta.

Pashchat Karma: Wipe the area with sterile gauze

The Gunjabeeja churna is mixed with water or Honey and applied with the **1.5 mm** or approximately **the thickness of a blade of grass (Truna pramana) also YavaPramana.**

The Lepa is allowed to stay at the site for 30 minutes and washed with water.

Follow up: The same procedure is done on the 1st, 15th and 30th day and 15 days of follow up period (45 days duration).

Group B: Platelet rich plasma (PRP) Therapy followed by Minoxidil solution.**Pre Operative****Room & equipment**

Clean, private procedural room. Staff with sterile gloves, antiseptic, gauze, tourniquet (if needed), vacutainers with anticoagulant (ACD or sodium citrate), 10–20 ml syringes, centrifuge, sterile transfer pipettes, 1 ml insulin syringes (30G), sterile drape, topical anesthetic (EMLA), ice pack.

Blood draw

- Typical blood volume: **10–20 ml** (adjust by treatment area). Draw into ACD-containing tubes; label with patient ID/time.

- **PRP preparation (common double-spin method)**
- **Soft spin (first spin)** to separate RBCs (typical ranges reported: ~1,400–1,700 rpm for 6–10 min)
- Transfer plasma + buffy coat to a sterile tube.
- **Hard spin (second spin)** to concentrate platelets (typical ranges 2,000–3,000 rpm for 8–15 min). Remove top platelet-poor plasma (PPP) and retain bottom PRP (~2–4 ml from 10–20 ml blood depending on kit).
- Activation is **optional** (e.g., calcium chloride) — many clinicians inject unactivated PRP; activation protocols vary. (Preparation parameters differ between devices/kits — select and validate your centrifuge settings for g-force per manufacturer or published protocol).
- **Preparing the scalp**
- Cleanse with antiseptic (povidone-iodine or chlorhexidine) and allow to dry. Apply topical anesthetic (if used) 30–45 minutes prior and remove/clean skin before injection.

Operative**Injection technique**

- Use **1 ml insulin syringes with 30G needles** for intradermal/subdermal injections.
- Typical volume per injection: **0.1–0.2 ml** per site. Spacing: **~1 cm** between injection points across the alopecic patch (nappage / multiple small intradermal blebs). Depth: intradermal to superficial subdermal (pin-point bleeding indicates appropriate depth 2 to 3mm depth)

Post-operative**Immediate (0–1 hour)**

- Observe for 15–30 minutes for vasovagal reaction or allergic signs (rare with autologous product). Provide ice packs for comfort.

First 24–72 hours

- **Do not wash** the treated area for **12–24 hours** (many protocols use 24 h). Avoid topical agents/irritants for 24–48 h. Avoid intense sun exposure, saunas, heavy sweating for 48 h. Use acetaminophen if pain is needed

Follow up

The procedure is done on 1st, 15th and 30th day and follow up period of 15 days (45 days duration).

Assessment Criteria

Assessment will be conducted based on both subjective and objective clinical parameters, recorded before and after treatment using a standardized clinical proforma.

- **Subjective Parameter**

Patchy hair loss
Itching

- **Objective Parameters**

Extent of patchy hairloss

RESULTS**Table: Overall changes from day 0 to day 45 in Group A and Group B.**

Parameters	Changes	Group A	Group B
Extent of patchy hair loss	Day 0-Day 15	36.0	16.0
	Day 0-Day 30	76.0	52.0
	Day 0-Day 45	88.0	68.0
Itching	Day 0-Day 15	40.0	22.2
	Day 0-Day 30	77.1	55.6
	Day 0-Day 45	94.3	81.5
Overall	Day 0-Day 45	91.14	74.74

Summary of Overall Changes from Day 0 to Day 45 in Group A and Group B

The comparative analysis of treatment outcomes over a 45-day period revealed that **Group A consistently demonstrated greater improvement** than Group B across all measured parameters.

- *Extent of Patchy Hair Loss*

- **Day 0–15:** Group A showed a 36.0% reduction, compared to 16.0% in Group B.
- **Day 0–30:** Group A improved by 76.0%, while Group B showed a 52.0% reduction.
- **Day 0–45:** Group A achieved an 88.0% reduction, surpassing Group B's 68.0%.

- *Itching*

- **Day 0–15:** Group A reduced itching by 40.0%, while Group B showed a 22.2% reduction.
- **Day 0–30:** Group A improved by 77.1%, compared to 55.6% in Group B.
- **Day 0–45:** Group A reached a 94.3% reduction, whereas Group B achieved 81.5%.

- *Overall Improvement*

- By Day 45, **Group A recorded a total improvement of 91.14%**, while **Group B reached 74.74%**.

Figure: Overall changes from before to follow up 2 in Group A and Group B.

**Pictures - Group B
Before Treatment**

After Treatment

Before treatment

After Treatment

Before Treatment

After Treatment

Pictures--Group A
Before treatment

After treatment

Before treatment

After Treatment

Medicine preparation

Fig no. 10 Gunja seeds

Making Pottali

Dolayantra swedana with Godugdha

Making Churna of shodhita gunja beeja

Fig no 11: Drying of Gunja beeja churna.

Fig no 12: Gunja lepana.

Fig no 13: Prachhanna procedure.

Fig no. 14: PRP Procedure.

Fig no. 15: Minoxidil 5 % topical application.

DISCUSSION

Discussion is the process of examining the facts through their merits and demerits to obtain proper knowledge about facts. With the support of the scientific aspect, discussion helps in establishing the concept. *Charakacharya* has precisely said that even the truth may not be accepted if it is without proper legal interpretation.

Indralupta is a disease affecting the *kapala* (scalp). *Tridoshas* along with *rakta* play a major role in the manifestation of the disease. It is characterized by loss of hair with poor replacement. According to *Ayurveda acharyas*, *pitta* associated with *vata* gets localized in the *romakupa* and causes hair fall. Later, *kapha dosha* associated with *rakta* causes obstruction to the hair roots and restricts hair regrowth.

The signs and symptoms described in the *classics of Ayurveda* for *Indralupta* and those of *Alopecia areata* mentioned in modern science are almost identical. Hence, *Indralupta* can be equated to *Alopecia areata*. *Alopecia areata* is an autoimmune disease mediated by T-lymphocytes directed against hair follicles. The natural history of *Alopecia areata* is not well known. Genetic predisposition and environmental factors may trigger the initiation of the disease.

There is a high frequency of family history in affected persons, ranging from 10% to 42% of cases. Available information indicates that 34% to 50% of patients with *Alopecia areata* will recover within one year, while 15% to 25% will progress to total loss of scalp and body hair, from which full recovery is uncommon. Some available treatments may induce hair regrowth but do not alter the overall course of the disease.

Modern science includes many treatments such as corticosteroids, Immunotherapy, Phototherapy, Serums, Topical anti hypertensives and Platelet rich plasma therapy etc. In this study the Platelet rich plasma therapy followed by minoxidil 5 % application was conducted in Standard group of 20 patients.

Ayurveda suggests surgical procedures such as *Siravyadha*, *Prachhanna*, and *Lekhana*, as well as para-surgical procedures like *Jalaukavacharana*^[83] in the management of *Indralupta*. A large number of drugs for external application, in the form of herbal, mineral, and single-drug preparations, are also described. Many curative and preventive measures such as *Nasya*, *Rasayana*, *Moordha Taila*^[84] (*Abhyanga*, *Pichu*, *Shirodhara*, *Shirobasti*), *Pathya Sevana*, and *Apathya Nisheda* are mentioned. However, no empirical data related to the efficacy of these trial drugs are available; hence, a clinical trial with proper documentation is essential for evaluating their therapeutic value. In this study *Prachhanna* followed by *Gunja lepa* was conducted as trial group for 20 patients.

The *Samprapti* of *Indralupta* involves two stages. The initial stage is characterized by excessive shedding of hair due to *Vata-Pitta Prakopa*. If noticed early at this stage, *Vata-Pittahara Brimhana Chikitsa* can be adopted. The condition then progresses to the next stage, with the involvement of *Kapha* and *Rakta*, leading to prevention of hair regrowth. Commonly, patients seek medical care during this stage.

The treatment plan adopted for the second stage aims at resolving *Srotorodha* through *Kapha-Rakta Shodhana*. However, local measures for resolving *Romakupa Rodha* are essential for *Samprapti Vighatana* in this stage. For

Ekadeshastha Rakta-Dushti, the adoptable modality is *Prachhanna*. *Prachhanna*^[85] stimulates local circulation and thus helps in the easy absorption of drugs applied as *Lepana*. *Prachhanna* is mentioned in *Indralupta* as it reaches hair follicles seated in the dermis and removes local obstruction caused by *Kapha* and *Raktha*. Then *Lepana* is applied.

Probable Mode of Action of Prachhanna Therapy in Alopecia Areata (Indralupta)

1. Ayurvedic Viewpoint

According to Ayurveda, *Indralupta* is primarily caused by vitiation of *Vata* and *Pitta doshas*, which in turn vitiates *Rakta dhatu*, leading to *Keshachyuti* (hair loss) and obstruction of the hair follicles by *Kapha* and *Rakta* vitiation.

Acharya Sushruta has advised *Raktamokshana* (bloodletting) as an effective line of treatment in *Raktaja rogas* and skin diseases (*Kushta*), which share a similar *Raktadushti* pathology. Among various *Raktamokshana* methods, *Prachhanna karma* — superficial incisions with a sharp instrument (lancet or scalpel) — is particularly effective for localized vitiation.

Mechanism in Ayurvedic Terms

- **Dosha Shamana (Pacification of vitiated Doshas):** *Prachhanna* removes vitiated *Rakta*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha* locally accumulated in the scalp region. This helps in pacifying the *Doshas* responsible for follicular blockage and inflammation.
- **Srotoshodhana (Clearing of Microchannels):** By letting out the vitiated blood, *Prachhanna* clears obstruction (*Sanga*) in the *Romakupa srotas* (hair follicular channels), restoring proper circulation of *Rakta* and *Rasa dhatu*s to the hair roots.
- **Rakta Shuddhi (Purification of Blood):** The removal of impure *Rakta* allows regeneration of healthy *Rakta dhatu*, leading to improved nourishment of *Twak* and *Kesha*.
- **Vata-Pitta-Samana and Kapha Shodhana:** The mild controlled trauma and bleeding reduce *Kapha* stagnation in follicles and normalize *Vata* movement in the region, helping new hair to grow.
- **Stimulation of Local Agni and Dhatu Pushti:** *Prachhanna* promotes *Dhatvagni* at the local site, thereby enhancing *Rasadhatu* and *Raktadhatu* metabolism, improving follicular nutrition, and stimulating new hair follicle activity.
- **Prevention of Recurrence:** By eliminating the localized *Dushta Rakta* and correcting *Srotorodha*,

Prachhanna prevents recurrence of follicular inflammation and hair fall.

2. Modern Scientific Correlation

Prachhanna karma can be understood as a controlled superficial micro-incision therapy leading to local bloodletting and micro-injury-induced healing response.

Probable Biomedical Mechanisms

- **Improved Local Microcirculation^[93]:** The micro-incisions cause transient bleeding and vascular dilation, leading to improved local perfusion. Enhanced blood supply increases oxygen and nutrient delivery to dormant hair follicles
- **Removal of Inflammatory Mediators:** The procedure may help drain out local inflammatory exudates, immune complexes, and pro-inflammatory cytokines (like IL-1, IL-6, TNF- α), reducing the autoimmune inflammation that attacks the hair follicle in Alopecia areata.
- **Stimulation of Hair Follicle Stem Cells^[94]:** The controlled micro-injury activates wound-healing cascades involving growth factors such as: – *VEGF* (Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor) – promotes angiogenesis around follicles – *IGF-1* (Insulin-like Growth Factor-1) and *FGF-7* (Fibroblast Growth Factor) – stimulate follicular proliferation – *PDGF* (Platelet-Derived Growth Factor) – enhances dermal papilla activity These collectively help in reactivation of hair follicle cycling from the telogen (resting) to anagen (growth) phase.
- **Modulation of Autoimmune Activity:** In Alopecia areata, cytotoxic T-cells attack the hair bulb. Microbleeding may locally alter immune cell activity and antigen presentation, leading to immunomodulation and restoration of immune privilege around the hair follicle.
- **Induction of Growth Factors Similar to Microneedling^[95]:** *Prachhanna* shares similar principles with modern microneedling therapy, known to enhance collagen remodeling and promote hair regrowth by upregulating stem cell factors (*Wnt/ β -catenin* pathway activation).
- **Reduction of Scalp Tension and Sebum Blockage:** The superficial incisions may relieve micro-tissue stiffness, help drainage of blocked sebaceous secretions, and improve follicular ventilation.

3. Integrated Understanding

Ayurvedic Concept	Modern Correlation	Effect on Disease Process
Raktamokshana (Removal of vitiated blood)	Reduction of local inflammatory mediators	Decreases autoimmune inflammation
Srotoshodhana (Channel cleansing)	Improved microcirculation	Enhances nutrient delivery to follicles
Vata-Pitta shaman	Modulation of neurovascular tone and immune activity	Reduces follicular stress and inflammation
Agni deepana and Dhatu poshana	Growth factor release and collagen remodeling	Stimulates follicular regeneration

4. SUMMARY

Thus, *Prachhanna Karma* acts both locally and systemically. It removes *Dushta Rakta*, normalizes *Vata-Pitta* imbalance, improves local *Rakta-sanchara* (circulation), and stimulates the physiological healing response. Modern correlation supports its role in improving microcirculation, immune modulation, and activating growth factors necessary for follicular regeneration. Hence, *Prachhanna therapy* serves as a potent, minimally invasive, and rational therapeutic approach in *Indralupta* (Alopecia areata).

Probable Mode of Action of Gunja Lepa in Alopecia Areata (Indralupta)

Lepana is a *bahiparimarjana chikitsa*.^[97] The drugs applied as *lepana* are absorbed by the action of *twakasrita Brajakagni*. The *lepana* which is applied over the scalp, by the effect of its *Rasa, Guna, Veerya*, and *Vipaka*, is absorbed by the hair follicles and in turn causes the pores to open up. By the *prabhava* of the drug, hair growth can be observed. *Prachhanna* drains out the vitiated blood from the *Srotus*, and later when *lepa* is applied over the region, it facilitates easy and faster absorption of the drug.

1. Ayurvedic View

Guñjā (Abrus precatorius Linn.) is described in *Ayurvedic classics* as a potent herb possessing *Tikta (bitter)*, *Katu (pungent)*, and *Kashaya (astringent) Rasas*, with *Ushna Veerya* (hot potency) and *Katu Vipāka* (pungent post-digestive effect). Its dominant actions include *Kaphahara, Vatahara*, and *Raktashodhaka*.

In *Indralupta*, vitiated *Vata* and *Pitta* doshas cause hair fall by disturbing *Rakta dhatu* and obstructing *Romakupa (hair follicles)* due to *Kapha* and *Rakta dushti*. *Guñjā*, by virtue of its *Katu-Ushna* and *Tikshna* properties, acts specifically on these pathogenic factors.

Ayurvedic Mechanism

1. Kaphavata Shamana (Pacification of Kapha and Vata)

The *Ushna* and *Tikshna guna* of *Guñjā* counteract *Kapha* obstruction and regulate *Vata* flow in *Romakupa*. This clears follicular blockage and facilitates the re-entry of *Rakta* and *Rasa dhatu* into the hair roots.

2. Rakta Shodhana (Blood Purification)

Guñjā is *Raktashodhaka* — it purifies the vitiated *Rakta dhatu* locally, which is essential in correcting the *Rakta dushti* that underlies *Indralupta*.

3. Lekhana and Shothahara Karma (Scraping and Anti-inflammatory Action)

The *Tikshna* and *Katu* qualities produce a mild *Lekhana* (scraping) effect that removes *Mala* and *Kapha* accumulation in the scalp region. This cleanses the follicular openings (*Romakupa mārga shodhana*), reducing *Shotha* (inflammation).

4. Keshya and Rasayana Effect (Hair-promoting and Rejuvenative)

With proper processing (e.g., *Shodhana* of *Guñjā* seeds), its *Keshya guna* helps in regeneration of new hair follicles and supports *Rasadhatu poshana* (nourishment of the plasma and blood tissues).

5. Stambhana and Vrana Ropana (Healing and Regenerative Action)

The *Kashaya rasa* aids in local healing and helps in the re-establishment of follicular health after removing *Dushta Rakta* and *Kapha* accumulation.

2. Modern Scientific Perspective

Modern pharmacological research on *Abrus precatorius* supports several actions relevant to the pathophysiology of *Alopecia areata*.

Probable Biomedical Mechanisms

1. Immunomodulatory and Anti-inflammatory Action

Alopecia areata is an autoimmune disorder where immune cells attack hair follicles.

- *Guñjā* contains **abrine, abrinine, glycyrrhizin-like alkaloids**, and **flavonoids** that exhibit *immunosuppressive and immunomodulatory effects*.
- These may downregulate pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1, IL-6, TNF- α) and inhibit lymphocytic infiltration around follicles, thus restoring the immune privilege of the hair bulb.

2. Counter-irritant and Circulatory Stimulant Effect

The *Tikshna ushna guna* causes mild local irritation when applied as *Lepa*, leading to vasodilation and increased microcirculation.

This enhanced blood flow improves nutrient and oxygen delivery to the hair follicle bulb, promoting the *Anagen (growth)* phase of the hair cycle — a mechanism comparable to *topical irritant therapies* used in modern dermatology (like DNCB or Anthralin).

3. Antioxidant and Free Radical Scavenging Action

Oxidative stress plays a major role in the autoimmune attack on hair follicles.

Guñjā seeds contain **flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and triterpenoids** with potent antioxidant properties, which neutralize reactive oxygen species (ROS) and protect follicular cells from oxidative damage.

4. Antimicrobial and Antifungal Effect

The antimicrobial compounds present in *Guñjā* help maintain scalp hygiene, prevent secondary infection, and promote a healthy scalp environment for hair regrowth.

5. Stimulation of Local Growth Factors

The mild inflammatory stimulus caused by *Guñjā Lepa* may trigger the release of local growth mediators such as **VEGF, FGF, and IGF-1**^[98], promoting angiogenesis

and follicular stem cell activation—mechanisms parallel to *microneedling-induced regeneration*.

6. Keratinocyte Activation and Collagen Remodeling

The local irritation may activate epidermal keratinocytes and dermal fibroblasts, leading to enhanced collagen turnover and regeneration of hair follicle structures.

3. Integrated Understanding

Ayurvedic Concept	Modern Correlation	Effect on Disease
<i>Kaphavata Shamana</i>	Reduction of follicular blockage and improved microcirculation	Reopens hair follicles
<i>Rakta Shodhana</i>	Anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory activity	Controls autoimmune inflammation
<i>Lekhana karma</i>	Mild exfoliation and local irritation	Promotes circulation and hair growth
<i>Keshya guna</i>	Growth factor stimulation and antioxidant activity	Regrowth of hair follicles
<i>Shothahara</i>	Reduction in local inflammation and edema	Normalizes scalp microenvironment

4. SUMMARY

Thus, Guñjā Lepa acts through both **Ayurvedic principles** and **modern physiological mechanisms**. It alleviates *Kapha-Vata dushti*, purifies *Rakta*, and stimulates *Romakupa*. The mild irritant and circulatory stimulant action promotes follicular regeneration, while its antioxidant and immunomodulatory effects help in reversing the autoimmune process of Alopecia areata. Collectively, these mechanisms restore normal follicular activity and promote hair regrowth in *Indralupta*.

5. Classical Reference

सुश्रुत संहिता (सूत्रस्थान 13/4)

“लेखनीयं च कफवातशमकं चोष्णं तीक्ष्णं च यत् लेपनं तत् रोमकूपविवर्तनं भवति”⁹⁹

— A Lepa with *Lekhana*, *Ushna*, and *Tikshna* properties clears the obstruction of hair follicles caused by *Kapha* and *Vata*.

This classical principle aptly explains how *Guñjā Lepa* acts by opening blocked *Romakupas*, allowing new hair growth.

Probable Mode of Action of PRP Therapy in Alopecia Areata (Indralupta)

Introduction

Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) therapy is an autologous biological treatment modality that utilizes a patient's own platelets to stimulate tissue regeneration and hair follicle growth. In Alopecia areata—a chronic autoimmune condition characterized by non-scarring patchy hair loss—PRP has shown promising results in promoting follicular regeneration and modulating local immune reactions.

From an Ayurvedic perspective, *Indralupta* is a *Raktapradoshaja Vyadhi* caused by vitiation of *Vata* and *Pitta doshas*, leading to *Rakta dushti* and obstruction of *Romakupa* (hair follicles) by *Kapha*. PRP therapy can be correlated to *Raktashodhana* and *Raktaprasadana*

Chikitsa, as it purifies and revitalizes the local *Rakta dhatu* and supports *Keshavridhi* (hair growth).

Modern Scientific Mechanism

PRP is a concentrated plasma fraction containing 3–5 times higher platelet count than peripheral blood, along with growth factors and cytokines crucial for tissue repair and follicular stimulation.

A. Growth Factor–Mediated Follicular Regeneration

Activated platelets release multiple bioactive growth factors such as.

- **PDGF (Platelet-Derived Growth Factor):** Promotes angiogenesis and fibroblast proliferation, improving follicular vascular supply.
- **VEGF (Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor):** Enhances microcirculation around the follicles, providing oxygen and nutrients necessary for the *Anagen* (growth) phase.
- **EGF (Epidermal Growth Factor):** Stimulates proliferation of keratinocytes and outer root sheath cells.
- **FGF (Fibroblast Growth Factor):** Encourages differentiation of dermal papilla cells and prolongs the anagen phase.
- **IGF-1 (Insulin-like Growth Factor-1):** Prevents premature follicular regression (*catagen phase inhibition*).
- **TGF-β (Transforming Growth Factor-β):** Modulates inflammation and aids in tissue remodeling.

These collectively reactivate dormant hair follicles, stimulate stem cell niches, and promote new hair shaft formation.

CONCLUSION

The present clinical study re affirms that *Indralupta*, as described in *Ayurvedic* texts, closely parallels *Alopecia areata* in modern dermatology, both in pathogenesis and

clinical presentation. The disease predominantly affects young adults and males, with a higher incidence among individuals consuming a mixed diet and those of *Vatapittaja prakruti*. While occupation, religion, and marital status showed no significant correlation, psychological stress and hormonal imbalances emerged as contributing factors.

Therapeutically, *Prachhanna karma* followed by *Guñjā lepa* demonstrated superior efficacy in reducing hair loss and associated symptoms compared to PRP therapy with Minoxidil 5%. The dual mechanism of mechanical stimulation and pharmacological action in Group A facilitated deeper follicular activation, enhanced microcirculation, and effective *Srotoshodhana*, resulting in accelerated hair regrowth and symptomatic relief.

The Ayurvedic rationale of *Dosha pacification*, *Rakta shodhana*, and *Romakupa vivartana* was validated through observable clinical outcomes and supported by modern correlations such as growth factor stimulation, immune modulation, and improved vascular perfusion. Despite occasional allergic reactions, the therapeutic potential of *Guñjā lepa* post-*Prachhanna* remains significant when properly purified and individualized.

These findings underscore the relevance of integrative approaches in managing autoimmune hair disorders and highlight the need for further studies with larger sample sizes, longer follow-up durations, and standardized protocols to establish reproducibility and long-term efficacy.

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